

Copper(II) Complexes of Hydroxyacetic Acid

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Copper(II) glycolate complexes with chloro and nitrate as anionic ligands, ammonia, morpholine, pyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline as neutral ligands and potassium as cation have been synthesized. The complexes are characterized by thermogravimetric analysis, magnetic susceptibility, electronic, infrared and epr spectral measurements.

HYDROXYACETIC acid, commonly known as glycolic acid, (HOCH_2COOH , glyH) is known to act as negatively charged chelating ligand towards metal ions through the oxygen atoms of the $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{COO}$ groups. Several hydrated and anhydrous metal glycolates¹⁻³ featuring transition metal ions have been synthesized; some of which are polymeric involving bidentate bridging carboxylate group, in addition to the bonding through the hydroxo group. Thus, the crystal structure analysis on *bis*(glycolato) copper(II) has revealed⁴ that Cu(II) in the complex is in an elongated tetragonally distorted octahedral environment. The aim of the present work is to isolate mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) glycolate with anionic and neutral ligands, possibly introducing the unidentate ligands in the apical position of the copper polyhedron.

Experimental

Preparation :

1. Chloroglycolatoaquocopper(II), $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{OH}_2$, was prepared by interacting an alcoholic solution of copper(II) chloride with 70% glycolic acid taken in 1 : 1 mole ratio. The resultant solution was stirred for some time and the separated bluish-green crystals were filtered, washed with acetone and dried. Anal : found, C 12.2, H 2.1, Cl 18.0, Cu 32.3%; calcd. for $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{ClCu}$, C 12.5, H 2.6, Cl 18.5, Cu 33.1%.

2. Nitratoglycolatoaquocopper(II), $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2\text{NO}_3 \cdot \text{OH}_2$, was prepared by following the same method as above by taking copper nitrate instead of copper chloride. Anal : found, C 10.4, H 2.1, Cu 28.8%; calcd. for $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NO}_7\text{Cu}$, C 11.0, H 2.3, Cu 29.1%.

3. Potassium dichloroglycolatoaquocuprate(II), $\text{K Cu}(\text{gly})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{OH}_2$, was obtained by adding to an alcoholic solution of CuCl_2 required amount of 70% glyH and KOH. The resultant solution was stirred at 70° for 10-15 min. The crystallized product was filtered, washed with acetone and dried.

Anal : found, C 8.9, H 2.2, Cl 25.6, Cu 23.0%; calcd. for $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{CuK}$, C 8.4, H 2.5, Cl 24.9, Cu 22.3%.

4. Potassium *tris*(glycolato) cuprate(II) monohydrate, $\text{K Cu}(\text{gly})_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, was obtained by interacting aqueous solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2$ with the required amount of glyH and KOH and concentrating the solution on a water bath. The separated crystals were filtered, washed with acetone and dried. Anal : found, C 23.8, H 3.8, Cu 21.1%; calcd. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_{10}\text{CuK}$, C 23.5, H 3.6, Cu 20.7%.

5. *Bis*(glycolato) diamminecopper(II), $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2$, was prepared by dissolving $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2$, obtained by the interaction of basic copper carbonate and glycolic acid, in aqueous ammonia. To the clear solution obtained was added acetone and the separated blue crystalline solid was collected on a filter, washed with acetone and dried. Anal : found, C 18.9, H 4.2, N 11.6, Cu 25.1%; calcd. for $\text{C}_4\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{Cu}$, C 19.4, H 4.9, N 11.3, Cu 25.7%.

6. *Bis*(glycolato)dimorpholinecopper(II), $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2(\text{morp})_2$, was obtained by following the same method as above using morpholine in place of ammonia. Anal : found, C 36.5, H 5.8, N 7.4, Cu 16.6%; calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{Cu}$, C 37.2, H 6.3, N 7.2, Cu 16.4%.

7. *Bis*(glycolato)dipyridinecopper(II), $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2(\text{py})_2$, was prepared by the interaction of $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2$ and pyridine following the procedure of ammonia adduct preparation. Anal : found, C 45.9, H 4.8, N 7.8, Cu 17.6%; calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{Cu}$, C 45.2, H 4.3, N 7.5, Cu 17.1%.

8. *Bis*(glycolato)(1,10-phenanthroline)copper(II), $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2(\text{phen})$, was obtained by interacting 1 : 1 mole ratio of $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2$ and 1,10-phenanthroline in alcoholic solution. The reactant mixture was stirred and acetone was added to precipitate the complex. The blue crystalline product obtained was filtered, washed with acetone and dried. Anal :

TABLE 1—TG DATA OF COPPER GLYCOLATE COMPLEXES

Complex	Temp. range, °C	Loss of H ₂ O or base, %		Temp. range, °C	Loss of glycolate, %		Final product
		Found	Calcd.		Found	Calcd.	
1.	120-200	9.0	9.4	220-540	58.0	57.6	CuO
2.	120-200	8.0	8.2	200-480	63.0	62.7	CuO
3.	—	—	—	200-600	38.0	38.0	KCl + CuO
4.	100-120	5.0	5.2	220-600	56.0	56.4	K ₂ CO ₃ + CuO
5.	110-215	14.0	14.0	220-500	67.0	67.0	CuO
6.	175-230	45.0	44.9	220-500	79.0	78.5	CuO
7.	150-220	43.0	42.6	220-500	80.0	78.6	CuO
8.	—	—	—	260-500	78.0	78.2	CuO

For Sl. No. refer to text.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC, ELECTRONIC AND EPR DATA OF COPPER GLYCOLATES

Compound	Magnetic moment (B.M.) μ_{eff}	Electronic spectra		Epr spectra		$G = (g_{11} - 2)/(g_1 - 2)$
		(kK)	g_{11}	g_1	g_1	
1.	1.93	13.8	2.30	2.10	3.0	
2.	2.09	13.8	2.27	2.08	3.4	
3.	2.11	16.4	2.28	2.10	2.8	
4.	1.86	16.5		2.26	—	
5.	1.87	15.6	2.29	2.14	2.06	
6.	2.01	14.21	2.23	2.08	2.9	
7.	2.00	14.69	2.31	2.10	3.1	
8.	1.99	15.15		2.27	—	

For Sl. No. refer to text.

 TABLE 3—PRINCIPAL IR FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF COPPER GLYCOLATES

	ν OH(water)	ν NH	ν OH(glycolate)	ν COO(asym)	ν COO(sym)	$\Delta\nu$ COO	ν CuO	ν Cu-Cl	ν Cu-N
1.	3320s 3200sh	—	3090sh	1570s	1400s	170	480s	295	—
2.	3300s 3200sh	—	3110s	1570s	1400s	170	450s	—	—
3.	3400s 3340s	—	3095s	1570s	1398s	172	480s	262	—
4.	3440s 3380s	—	3100sh	1578s	1375s	200	400s	—	—
5.	—	3200s	3100sh	1585s	1380s	205	470s	—	440
6.	—	3100s	3060s	1580s	1400s	180	400s	—	255
7.	—	—	3000s	1580s	1390s	190	450s	—	264
8.	—	—	3040s	1580s	1400s	180	416s	—	244

For Sl. No. refer to text.

s—strong, m—medium, w—weak, sh—shoulder.

found, C 48.1, H 3.9, N 7.7, Cu 15.8%; calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₆Cu, C 48.6, H 3.6, N 7.1, Cu 16.1%.

Physical measurements: The thermogravimetric analysis of the complexes was carried out on a Stanton recording thermobalance at a linear heating rate of 6° per min.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature using Guoy balance and the μ_{eff} values were calculated after applying diamagnetic corrections⁸. The visible spectra of solid complexes were taken on a Carl Zeiss DMR 21 spectrophotometer in nujol emulsion. The infrared spectra were recorded using KBr pellet and nujol

mull techniques in Perkin-Elmer 257 and Beckman IR 12 spectrophotometers. The epr measurements were carried out on a Varian E-4 spectrometer at the X-band using DPPH as a g marker. The spectral data are given in Tables 2 and 3.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are insoluble in common solvents such as acetone, alcohol, benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, nitromethane and the insolubility precluded the conductance, the solution spectral measurements and the molecular weight determination. The complexes dissociate in water to give Cu(gly)₂ as one of the products. The X-ray

powder patterns taken with a Debye-Scherrer camera using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation suggest that they are crystalline compounds.

Thermogravimetric studies: The TG data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The weight loss curve indicates that $\text{K}[(\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2)_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ dehydrates at 100° suggesting water is present in the complex as lattice water. The other aquo complexes dehydrate above 120° suggesting the coordination of water in these complexes to copper. The adducts of ammonia, morpholine, and pyridine deaminate in the temperature range $110\text{--}200^\circ$ giving $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2$ as the product. The glycolate moiety starts decomposing in all the complexes above 220° . The phenanthroline adduct decomposes above 240° in a single step to give CuO as the final product at 500° . The end product of decomposition obtained around 600° is found, by weight loss curves and chemical analysis, to be CuO in the case of chloro nitrate and base adduct complexes, a mixture of KCl and CuO for $\text{K}[\text{Cu}(\text{gly})\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{OH}_2]$ and, K_2CO_3 and CuO for $\text{K}[\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The nitrate complex decomposes with a mild explosion due to the oxidative property of nitrate towards organic group.

Magnetic and spectral studies: The effective magnetic moments of the complexes measured at room temperature are in the range 1.9 to 2.0 B.M. suggesting they are magnetically normal with an unpaired electron as expected for $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$. It has been fairly well established⁶ that the electronic transitions in the region 14-16 kK are the characteristic of hexa- and penta-coordinated $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$. The asymmetric broad single absorptions with the peak maxima in the range 13-14 kK, observed for the complexes indicate that they are either 5-coordinate or 6-coordinate copper(II) complexes.

The epr spectra of $\text{K}[\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2(\text{phen})$ give a single isotropic line similar⁷ to that of $\text{Cu}(\text{en})_2\text{SO}_4$ suggesting a tetragonally distorted copper(II) with Jahn-Teller distortion in these complexes. The epr spectrum of ammonia complex is reproduced in Fig. 1. As seen from the Fig. 1, the spectrum shows three g values typical of rhombic symmetry indicating $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ in a rhombic octahedral environment with probably glycolate rings in a plane and two NH_3 molecules occupying the axial positions. The epr spectra of other complexes suggest that there is anisotropy with axial symmetry and the g factors indicate that $d_{x^2-y^2}$ is the ground state with $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ in an elongated tetragonal octahedral or square pyramidal stereochemistry⁸.

It is reported⁹ that the magnitude of G value is an indication of exchange interactions in the copper complexes. Thus when $G < 4$, there is significant exchange coupling¹⁰ present in the complexes. In the present compounds though the G values are

Fig. 1. Epr spectrum of $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2$.

less than 4, the interaction may be very weak as the magnetic moment of these complexes are normal at room temperature. However, low temperature magnetic measurements should throw more light on this aspect.

The principal infrared frequencies of the complexes are given in Table 3. The broad band observed at 3440 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $\text{K}[\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is assigned¹¹ to ν_{OH} of lattice water. The other aquo complexes exhibit ν_{OH} in the range $3400\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The splitting and shifting of ν_{OH} bond to lower frequency region¹¹ confirms the ligation of H_2O to the metal. Likewise, 3280 and 3200 cm^{-1} bands of $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2$ and 3100 cm^{-1} band of $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2(\text{morp})_2$ are assigned to ν_{NH} frequencies of NH_3 and morpholine. The appearance of these frequencies at lower energy region suggests the bonding of these bases to copper in their complexes.

The spectral frequencies of the glycolate group in the complexes appear more or less in the same region¹ as that of $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2$. The ν_{OH} of the free glyH appears around 3400 cm^{-1} which is shifted to 3100 cm^{-1} in the complexes. The asymmetric stretching frequency of $-\text{COO}$ is shifted from 1710 to 1570 cm^{-1} in the complexes suggesting the chelation of the ligand. The separation between asymmetric and symmetric COO vibrations ($\Delta\nu_{\text{COO}}$) is an indication of the nature of carboxylate bonding to the metal in metal carboxylate. Thus, it has been accepted by several authors¹² that the covalent character of M-O bond increases with an increase of ($\Delta\nu_{\text{COO}}$) values. The carboxylate group when acting as a bridge ligand, involves the

coordination of the carbonyl oxygen $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \rightarrow \text{M} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ \text{O} - \text{M} \end{array}$

and as the strength of the M-O bond increases, there will be decrease in the ($\Delta\nu_{\text{COO}}$) value. If the interaction is mainly ionic, the ($\Delta\nu_{\text{COO}}$) value will be minimum. In order to find out the type of carboxylate bonding in the complexes the infrared spectrum of lithium glycolate is used for comparison. Ligly exhibits asymmetric and symmetric ν_{COO} vibrations at 1570 and 1425 cm^{-1} respectively, with the ($\Delta\nu_{\text{COO}}$) value of 145 cm^{-1} . As seen from the Table 3, the value is greater ($\sim 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) for base adducts and trisglycolate complexes, whereas it is around 170 cm^{-1} for other complexes. This suggests that in the base adducts and trisglycolate complexes, the glycolate group is acting as bidentate chelate and in others probably it acts as terdentate by bonding through the carbonyl oxygen to the adjacent copper in addition to chelation.

The low energy bands around 400 and 300 cm^{-1} are assigned¹ primarily to Cu-O stretching mode. The medium intensity bands located at 420 and 250 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2$ are due to $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ and $\delta_{\text{N-Cu-N}}$ respectively as observed^{1,3} in $\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{SO}_4$. The bands observed around 250 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ as reported^{1,3} in literature for similar metal-amine complexes. In the chloro complexes the bands appearing in the region 260-300 cm^{-1} are assigned^{14,15} to $\nu_{\text{Cu-Cl}}$ of the terminal chlorine. The appearance of infrared bands at 1380 and 820 cm^{-1} due to ν_{NO} for the nitrate complex suggests¹⁶ the monodenticity of the nitrate group towards copper.

References

1. A. J. FISHINGER, A. SARAFU and A. L. COMPANION, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 2629.
2. K. NAKAMOTO, P. J. MCCARTHY and B. MINIATUS, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, **21**, 379.
3. A. J. FISHINGER and E. L. WEBB, *Chem. Comm.*, 1969, 407.
4. C. K. PROUT, R. A. ARMSTRONG, J. R. CARRUTHERS, J. G. FORRST, P. MURRAY-RUST and F. J. C. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 2791.
5. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILINS, *Modern Coordination Chemistry*, Interscience, New York, 1964, p. 403.
6. A. MONTENARO and C. Pellizzi, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1972, **6**, 644.
7. B. J. HATHAWAY, M. J. BEW, D. E. BILLING, R. J. DUDLEY and P. NICHOLLS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 2312.
8. B. J. HATHAWAY and D. E. BILLING, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 143.
9. I. M. PROCTOR, B. J. HATHAWAY and P. NICHOLLS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1678.
10. J. C. EISENSTEIN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1958, **28**, 323.
11. K. NAKAMOTO, *Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds*, II Ed., Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970.
12. K. NAKAMOTO, Y. MORIMOTO and A. E. MARTEL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4528 and references therein.
13. I. NAKAGAWA and T. SHIMANOCHI, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1960, **12**, 759.
14. M. GOLDSSTEIN, E. F. MONEY, A. ANDERSON and H. A. GEBBIE, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, **21**, 105.
15. R. WHYMAN, W. E. HATFIELD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1859.
16. N. F. CURTIS and Y. M. CURTIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 804.